

CRITICAL PERIOD HYPOTHESIS OF LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: this article defines that about critical period hypothesis of language development. Moreover, there are given much information based on Critical hypothesis of language improvement.

Key words: hypothesis, language acquisition, language learning, critical period.

What is the critical period hypothesis? This hypothesis is an important element of the study of language acquisition, or the ability of humans to learn languages. The critical period hypothesis states that there is a relatively short space of time in an individual's early life during which it is possible to learn a second language with native-like fluency. People learning a new language after this point, the hypothesis states, will always make certain predictable errors and will likely speak their second language with an accent. The exact critical period definition (the number of years during which people can successfully learn a new language) is up for debate. The original researchers suggested that nine years of age was the upper limit for native-like language learning, while newer research suggests that the critical period might extend to the age of seventeen or eighteen.

According to Penfield, Roberts, and later researchers, the critical period of language development exists for a specific reason. Young children are better at learning new languages because they have a lot of **neuroplasticity**, which means that the brain is more adaptable and more open to learning new information. After the critical period, older language learners tend to struggle in particular with grammatical systems, never quite absorbing all of nuance of a new language's grammar.

Besides neuroplasticity, there are two major factors in the critical period. The first is opening: a child must have the right environment and stimuli to begin learning a first or second language. This means that they need consistent exposure to the target

language and a supportive learning structure. The second major factor is closure, which is the time when the critical period ends. There are several theories that seek to explain why and exactly when the critical period ends. Some researchers have suggested that the myelination of neurons impacts the brain's ability to learn, effectively locking in the elements of language that have already been learned.

Wilder Penfield and fellow researcher Lamar Roberts published research in 1959 that first proposed the critical period hypothesis. Their research suggested that in order to learn a second language fluently, children must begin learning it before the age of nine. Penfield and Roberts also discussed the critical period in relation to learning a first language. They argued that a child who did not learn a first language by age nine would not only fail to learn a new language with native-like fluency, but would in fact never be able to acquire more than a basic linguistic understanding, regardless of future study.

Critical Factors of Language Development

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Criticisms of the Critical Period for Language Acquisition

The critical period for language acquisition is a significant theory that has been supported by further research. However, some researchers have criticized some or all of the theory based on their own studies. David Singleton, a researcher from Trinity College, Dublin, studied bilingual adults who learned a second language after the age of nine and found that some of them had managed to learn the language without encountering the problems Penfield and Roberts initially posed.

All in all, other studies have noted that adults actually do learn new languages with similar fluency to children, particularly if they are able to do so in a sufficiently immersive environment. They may even be better language students in some ways because of their metacognition abilities and understanding of linguistic structures. Ultimately, language learning is a complex topic influenced by many factors, including environment, social factors, and personal motivation. The critical period hypothesis is one important part of this field of study.

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